

Lastly, it is found that a nitro group in *para* position to a hydroxyl group is specially reactive and the condensation with primary arylamines takes place with ease, and even in absence of a condensation agent (cf. J. Houben and W. Fische, *ibid.*, p. 427).

A few arylamino derivatives of alizarin have now been obtained by condensing 4-nitroalizarin with the following primary aromatic amines: (a) aniline, (b) *o*-nitroaniline, (c) *p*-nitroaniline, (d) *m*-nitroaniline, (e) *p*-toluidine, (f) α -naphthylamine, (g) β -naphthylamine.

The general structural formula for the arylamino derivatives obtained is represented by.

(where R = aryl or substituted aryl or naphthyl residue), and is based on the following evidence:—

(a) The analytical results show that the nitrogen content corresponds to the presence of one and only one arylamino residue introduced into the alizarin molecule. This excludes the possibilities wherein one of the hydroxyl groups is replaced by the arylamino group. (These products would contain an additional N atom as NO_2 .)

(b) The possibility that the condensation product might carry an arylamino group in the *meso* position is also ruled out as these products have been subjected to alkaline hydrolysis which is known to eliminate such groups in *meso* position (Barry-Barnett, "Anthracene", p. 202).

(c) Lastly, the presence of two free hydroxyl groups is indicated by the solubility of the products in alkali and the formation of a crystalline dibenzoyl derivative in the case of each of the products.

The arylamino compounds obtained with the three nitroanilines and carrying a NO_2 group were reduced with zinc and 50% acetic acid to the corresponding amino derivatives. The benzoyl derivatives of these arylamino compounds have been obtained. The dyeing properties of the arylamino derivatives of alizarin and of their benzoyl derivatives have been studied. The former were used as mordant dyes (Al-mordant) and the latter as vat dyes. The vatting was effected with hydrosulphite in a dilute solution of sodium silicate at 40°.

The dyeing tests thus indicate that the introduction of arylamino and nitroarylamino residues into the alizarin molecule does not enhance its tinctorial property although the nitroarylamino derivatives give brighter shades than those obtained with the arylamino derivatives.

It is known that sulphonation of these compounds would give rise to dyes with powerful tinctorial properties. Work in this connection is being carried out and is in progress in our laboratory.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Preparation of the Arylamino Derivatives.—The arylamino derivatives were all obtained by the following general method, with minor variations. An intimate mixture of 4-nitroalizarin (5 g.), dry boric acid (4 g.) and an excess of the amine was heated with an air condenser on an oil-bath at 120° for 8 hours. The reaction mixture was then cooled and treated with dilute HCl, boiled and filtered. The treatment with boiling hydrochloric acid was repeated till the excess of the amine was completely removed. The residue was then dissolved in 30 ml. of warm 5% NaOH and reprecipitated with dilute HCl. It was finally washed with water till free of the acid, dried and crystallised twice from pyridine.

4-Phenylaminoalizarin (I) was obtained by condensing 4-nitroalizarin with aniline by the procedure described above. It formed dark brown needles, m.p. 215°, yield 61%. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids. With concentrated H₂SO₄ it gives a red solution. Its solution in NaOH is violet. An 1% dye shade was obtained on cotton mordanted with alum; it was deep violet. (Found: C, 72.92; H 4.01; N, 4.37. C₂₀H₁₃O₄N requires C, 72.51; H, 3.94; N, 4.23 per cent).

4-Phenylaminodibenzoylalizarin.—The above compound (I, 3 g.) was intimately mixed with 3 g. of fused sodium acetate and the mixture added to 30 ml. of hot nitrobenzene; 5 ml. of benzoyl chloride were then added and the whole refluxed on a sand-bath for 6 hours. On cooling, the dibenzoyl derivative separated out. It was filtered and washed with petrol till free of nitrobenzene and then boiled with water several times to remove Na acetate and benzoic acid, and finally crystallised from benzene as brown needles, m.p. 198°, yield 64%.

It gives a blood-red solution with H₂SO₄ (conc.). Warm NaOH hydrolyses it and gives a violet coloured solution. With "hydros" in dilute solution of Na₂SiO₃ at 40°, it gave a pink vat. A pale violet dye shade was obtained after dyeing. (Found: C, 75.21; H, 4.11; N, 2.57. C₂₄H₂₁O₆N requires C, 75.70; H, 3.90; N, 2.60 per cent).

4-(p-Tolyl)-aminoalizarin (II) was obtained by condensing 4-nitroalizarin with *p*-toluidine. It formed brown needle shaped crystals, m.p. 204°, yield 67%. It is insoluble in dilute acids. With H₂SO₄ (conc.) a reddish brown solution is obtained. With NaOH it gives a violet coloration. It is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid. An 1% dye shade was obtained on cotton mordanted with Al, which gave a brownish violet shade. (Found: C, 73.63; H, 4.49; N, 4.33. C₂₁H₁₅O₄N requires C, 73.04; H, 4.35; N, 4.06 per cent).

4-(p-Tolyl)-aminodibenzoylalizarin was obtained by the benzoylation of (II) by the procedure adopted in the case of (I). It formed light brown needles, m.p. 239°, yield 69%. With H₂SO₄ (conc.) it gives a red solution; warm NaOH produces a violet solution. On reduction with "hydros" in dilute Na₂SiO₃ solution at 40° a pink vat was obtained. A pale violet dye shade was obtained after dyeing. (Found: C, 75.83; H, 4.25; N, 2.74. C₂₅H₂₃O₆N requires C, 75.95; H, 4.16; N, 2.53 per cent).

4-(o-Nitrophenyl)-aminoalizarin (III) was obtained by the condensation of 4-nitroalizarin with *o*-nitroaniline as described above. It formed orange coloured prisms, m.p. 272°, yield 60%.

It is insoluble in dilute acids. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) it forms a deep orange solution; it dissolves in NaOH with a blue colour. An 1% dye shade was obtained on cotton mordanted with Al. A pink dye shade was developed. (Found: C, 64.01; H, 3.32; N, 7.56. $C_{20}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires C, 63.83; H, 3.19; N, 7.45 per cent).

4-(*o*-Nitrophenyl)-aminodibenzoylizarin was obtained by the benzylation of (III) by the procedure as under (I). It formed golden yellow needles, m.p. 257° , yield 61%. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) it forms a brown solution; warm NaOH gives a blue solution. With 'hydros' in a weakly alkaline solution, it gives a reddish brown vat. A brownish red shade was obtained after dyeing. (Found: C, 70.12; H, 3.39; N, 4.72. $C_{34}H_{20}O_8N_4$ requires C, 69.86; H, 3.42; N, 4.79 per cent).

4-(*o*-Aminophenyl)-aminoalizarin was obtained by reduction of (III). The compound (III, 5 g.) was added to 60 ml. of 50% acetic acid and then 3 g. of Zn dust. The reduction was allowed to proceed for 2 hours. Dilute HCl (40 ml.) was then added to the reaction mixture to dissolve the excess of Zn. On dilution with water, the amino compound separated out; it was filtered, washed at the pump with water, dried and crystallised from alcohol, as red needles, m.p. 221° , yield 75%.

It dissolves in H_2SO_4 (conc.) giving a dark red solution. It is also soluble in NaOH with violet coloration. An 1% shade was obtained on cotton mordanted with Al. A light pink shade was obtained. (Found: C, 69.31; H, 4.16; N, 8.20. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires C, 69.36; H, 4.05; N, 8.09 per cent).

4-(*m*-Nitrophenyl)-aminoalizarin (IV) was obtained by condensing 4-nitroalizarin with *m*-nitroaniline as described under (I). It formed light red needles, m.p. 269° , yield 72%. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) a light brown solution is formed. NaOH solution gives a blue coloration. An 1% dye shade was obtained on cotton mordanted with Al. A pink dye shade was obtained. (Found: C, 63.98; H, 3.10; N, 7.27. $C_{22}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires C, 63.83; H, 3.19; N, 7.45 per cent).

4-(*m*-Nitrophenyl)-aminodibenzoylizarin was obtained by the benzylation of (IV) as in the case of (I). It formed yellow needles, m.p. above 310° , yield 63%. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) it gives a brown solution. It dissolves in warm NaOH with a blue solution. On reduction with 'hydros' it gives a reddish brown vat. A brownish red shade was obtained after dyeing. (Found: C, 70.0; H, 3.51; N, 4.91. $C_{34}H_{20}O_8N_4$ requires C, 69.86; H, 3.42; N, 4.79 per cent).

4-(*m*-Aminophenyl)-aminoalizarin was obtained by the reduction of (IV) with Zn and 50% acetic acid as in the case of (III). It formed deep orange coloured needles, m.p. 235° , yield 72%. It does not dissolve in dilute mineral acids, but is soluble in warm acetic acid giving a red solution. It is soluble in NaOH solution with a violet coloration. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) it gives a dark red solution. An 1% dye shade was obtained on cotton mordanted with Al. It gave a light pink shade. (Found: C, 69.08; H, 4.17; N, 7.96. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires C, 69.36; H, 4.05; N, 8.09 per cent).

4-(*p*-Nitrophenyl)-aminoalizarin (V) was obtained by condensing 4-nitroalizarin with *p*-nitroaniline as described above. It formed orange needles, m.p. 253° , yield 75%. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids but dissolves in acetic acid. With H_2SO_4 (conc.)

it gives a brown solution, and with NaOH a violet solution. An 1% dye shade was obtained on cotton mordanted with Al. A red shade was obtained. (Found: C, 64.02; H, 3.28; N, 7.59. $C_{20}H_{12}O_6N_2$ requires C, 63.83; H, 3.19; N, 7.45 per cent).

4-(*p*-Nitrophenyl)-aminodibenzoylizarin was obtained by the benzoylation of (V), as in the case of (I). It formed yellow plates, m.p. 282°, yield 65%. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) it gives a reddish brown solution; it dissolves in warm NaOH solution with a blue colour. Reduction with 'hydros' gives a reddish brown vat. Mercerised cotton dyed in a 2% dye bath gave a brownish red dye shade. (Found: C, 69.41; H, 3.75; N, 4.70. $C_{24}H_{20}O_8N_2$ requires C, 69.86; H, 3.42; N, 4.79 per cent).

4-(*p*-Aminophenyl)-aminoalizarin was obtained by the reduction of (V) as in the case of (III). It formed red prisms, m.p. 185-87°, yield 78%. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) it forms a blood-red solution; it dissolves in NaOH solution with a violet colour. An 1% dye shade was obtained with cotton mordanted with Al. A light pink shade was obtained. (Found: C, 69.22; H, 4.17; N, 7.38. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires C, 69.36; H, 4.05; N, 8.09 per cent).

4-(α -Naphthyl)-aminoalizarin (VI) was obtained by condensing 4-nitroalizarin with α -naphthylamine as described under (I). It formed greenish yellow prisms, m.p. 219°, yield 75%. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) it gives a deep red solution. It is soluble in NaOH solution with a violet coloration. An 1% dye shade was obtained on cotton mordanted with Al. A pink shade was obtained. (Found: C, 75.68; H, 3.83; N, 3.79. $C_{24}H_{18}O_4N$ requires C, 75.60; H, 3.94; N, 3.67 per cent).

4-(α -Naphthyl)-aminodibenzoylizarin was obtained by the benzoylation of (VI) as in the case of (I). It formed brown plates, m.p. 240°, yield 62%. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) it gives a deep red solution. It dissolves in warm NaOH solution with violet colour. On reduction with 'hydros' in weakly alkaline solution it gave a blue vat. A violet dye shade was obtained. (Found: C, 77.58; H, 3.81; N, 2.49. $C_{28}H_{24}O_8N$ requires C, 77.42; H, 3.90; N, 2.38 per cent).

4-(β -Naphthyl)-aminoalizarin (VII) was obtained by condensing 4-nitroalizarin with β -naphthylamine as described under (I). It formed reddish brown needles, m.p. 227°, yield 70%. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) it gives a blood red solution; in warm NaOH solution a blue colour is developed. An 1% dye shade was obtained on cotton mordanted with Al. The dye shade was pink. (Found: C, 75.79; H, 4.06; N, 3.62. $C_{24}H_{18}O_4N$ requires C, 75.60; H, 3.94; N, 3.67 per cent).

4-(β -Naphthyl)-aminodibenzoylizarin was obtained by the benzoylation of (VII) as in the case of (I). It formed brown prisms, m.p. 302°, yield 60%. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) a red solution is formed. It dissolves in warm NaOH giving a violet solution. Reduction with 'hydros' in a weakly alkaline solution gives a bluish violet vat. A 2% dye shade on mercerised cotton gave a violet shade. (Found: C, 77.63; H, 3.78; N, 2.29. $C_{32}H_{28}O_8N$ requires C, 77.42; H, 3.90; N, 2.38 per cent).